

TRAFFICKING IN HUMAN BEINGS

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Annotation: *this article provides information about the problem, consequence and solution of human trafficking.*

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Trafficking in human beings, one of the global problems that threatens the dignity, life and well-being of people today, remains a problem. Sadly, millions of people are victims of human trafficking, despite extensive legal advocacy efforts to prevent it. Therefore, this problem is considered not only as a local but also as an international issue. So what is the reason for this? One of the reasons for the development of this crime is that citizens do not have enough information about the procedures for traveling and working abroad, and fall into the trap of fraudsters.

According to the United Nations, there are more than 20 million victims of human trafficking in the world today. Every year, more than four million people are detained and physically exploited against their will. Although sexual exploitation is a relatively common form of human trafficking, hundreds of thousands of victims are victims of forced labor, domestic service, and children for begging or for body parts. This type of illegal activity has become the most lucrative business in the world. According to international experts, the annual income of illegal "traders" trading in "living people" is about \$ 150 billion.

Extensive work is being done in our country to combat this global scourge. It should be noted that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Trafficking in Human Beings" adopted on April 17, 2008 and the Presidential Decree "On Measures to Increase the Effectiveness of Combating Trafficking in Human Beings" of July 8, 2008 The resolution "On measures" serves as an important legal basis in resolving the issue and in this regard. The resolution defines "human trafficking" as follows:

"Trafficking in human beings is the use of force, threats or use of force or other forms of coercion, theft, fraud, deception, abuse of power or the use of risk of the situation or payment for the consent of another person or recruiting, transporting, handing over, concealing, or accepting people for the purpose of exploiting them in exchange for ransom. involuntary condition or separation of human organs or tissues.

Chapter 2, Article 5 of the Decision on Who Solves the Trafficking in Persons:

"Organizing the fight against human trafficking. The government agencies directly involved in the fight against human trafficking are: The decision to amend the Anti-Trafficking Act was passed by the Legislative Chamber on June 11, 2020.

According to the resolution approved by the Senate on August 7, 2020:

"A victim of trafficking in human beings is a natural person who has been a victim of trafficking in human beings, regardless of whether he or she has consented to such an act or whether he or she has participated in criminal proceedings;

Identification of victims of trafficking in human beings - a set of measures aimed at obtaining information about the commission or intent to commit acts against individuals, qualified as human trafficking; the fight against trafficking in human beings - activities aimed at preventing, detecting, combating and mitigating the consequences of trafficking in human beings, and providing assistance to victims of trafficking in human beings. " From a legal point of view, it is appropriate to dwell on the sanctions provided for in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan for this type of crime.

Trafficking in human beings. According to Article 135 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, trafficking in human beings, ie recruitment, transportation, transfer, concealment or reception of a person for the purpose of human trafficking, is punishable by three to five years' imprisonment or three to five years' imprisonment.

Isolation of human organs or tissues. According to Article 133 of the Criminal Code, up to three hundred and sixty hours of compulsory community for the removal of limbs or tissues for transplantation or preservation (preservation) for scientific or educational purposes without the consent of close relatives during or after the death of a person. or up to three years in prison.

Sexual exploitation. Part 1 of Article 131 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for a number of penalties for sexual misconduct, including: one will be appointed:

- A fine of fifty to seventy times the minimum wage;
- Compulsory public works from three hundred and sixty hours to four hundred and eighty hours;
- There are penalties such as one to three years in prison. In order to protect human rights and interests, July 30 of each year is widely celebrated around the world as Anti-Trafficking Day.

The measures taken are partially justified. For example, according to a representative of the Youth Union, to date, 43 young people who have been deceived abroad and have had their passports confiscated have had their passports returned, 18 have been repatriated, and 8 have been recruited by unknown organizations. "They were prevented from leaving the country."

In conclusion, we need a strong will and common sense to fight human trafficking, which is a sore point in the world. In the fight against human trafficking,

various segments of the population, especially women and minors, should be educated about the dangers and negative consequences of human trafficking, such as human trafficking, in populated areas, neighborhoods, One of the main tasks is to carry out propaganda and advocacy work in various educational institutions, government agencies, enterprises, institutions, organizations, to carry out extensive explanatory work, to raise legal awareness and legal culture in them.

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